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Balancing a change management process
A case study of how to approach curriculum change in higher education

N Svarre Kristensen
Research assistant
Aalborg University
Copenhagen, Denmark
E-mail: nsk@create.aau.dk

LB Andreasen
Associate professor
Aalborg University
Copenhagen, Denmark
E-mail: lba@hum.aau.dk

L Busk Kofoed
Part-time lecturer, Professor Emeritus
Aalborg University
Copenhagen, Denmark
E-mail: lk@create.aau.dk

JR Bruun-Pedersen
Assistant professor
Aalborg University
Copenhagen, Denmark
E-mail: jpe@create.aau.dk

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ABSTRACT

As part of a research project on possible future directions for problem-based learning (PBL) in a digital age, experiments are made to develop a flipped and integrated semester at a BSc engineering programme in Media Technology. The aim of the experimental research is to create a curriculum structure that integrates courses, student projects, and digital resources. This paper investigates how to approach the development of a new semester design with an active involvement of the teachers in the process. In the specific experiment, a planned organizational change management process, based on action research was established to develop a new semester concept and facilitate the teachers' development process, in co-creation with the research team. This process, however, was too far from the existing collaboration culture, and too time demanding for the teacher team. A change in the managing approach was made; a bricolage approach 'doing things with what is at hand' was

integrated in the change management process. To illustrate this management process, the data is gathered during the development process, as well as during the first parts of the 2019 spring semester. The empirical data body is consolidated through summaries from development meetings, interviews with teachers, and surveys with student participants. The balance between a planned management approach and an emergent ad hoc management approach, showed to become essential for working with the project goals of creating a flipped and integrated semester.

1 INTRODUCTION

Practicing planned organizational change management (POCM) [1], in this case reviewing how to approach the development of a new semester design, means entering a difficult management process. How to strategically approach change is evidentially impactful as the US national research council reports that 70% of all major organizational change strategies in business, government and educational institutions, fail within two years and are abandoned [2]. The change strategy chosen in this experimental research project has been informed by Kurt Lewin's three step model, developed in 1946 [3], involving the steps of unfreezing-change-refreezing. The quantity of change management models abounds today, but a literature review by Rosenbaum et al. reveals that the 13 most used models all have clear links to Lewin's model from 1946. The affiliated models since developed have provided refinements and more detailed explanations, but the authors argue that no fundamental changes have been made since Lewin's model [1]. The change process for a 4th semester university program, Medialogy has consequently been designed with roots in Lewin's model, based on action research. However, the design for change meets unexpected obstacles in the 'change' step, due to time priorities and the need for autonomy in the change process. This paper will examine the balance of managing a planned organizational change process, while implementing a more emergent and ad hoc, bricolage approach to the change process. The bricolage approach is a less pre-planned approach, and to move between the emergent bricolage approach and the mere POCM approach, became an important part of the intervention on 4th semester Media Technology at Aalborg University.

2 BACKGROUND

Aalborg University is known for its Problem Based Learning (PBL) approach, where disciplinary knowledge provided by courses are supporting and applied in the student-led, problem-oriented semester projects. In 2010 the problem- and project-based learning model at the university was reformed. Different structural problems regarding examination of group-based vs. individual performance, standardization of accreditation requirements, adjustment to the Bologna Directive and accountants for a new grading scale, put pressure on the previous model for PBL. Hence, a new model were deployed, where courses and semester projects are largely assessed separately [4]. After the reformed model, the focus on practicing the PBL principles has been criticized for being diluted [5]. Problems with routinisation of the project work has been pointed out, and a risk of putting more emphasis on the disciplinary course work than the problem-oriented semester project work has been notified [5].

In an ongoing research project "PBL Future - Future directions of PBL in a digital age" (2017-2020), a subproject seeks insights and solutions to this problem through a case

study at the BSc media technology engineering programme (Medialogy). Here, a combination of new digital learning tools are explored, along with experimentation on how to establish an improved structural integration of both disciplinary courses and the student-led semester project work. With a focus on how the structural integration of courses and projects on a full semester is affecting the support of PBL, a flipped and integrated semester was agreed to be planned and developed in collaboration between teachers and a research team. The flipped and integrated semester should build on two initiatives; 1) using a flipped learning approach to create more time for active learning in the classroom [6] and 2) an integration initiative. The process of managing this change will be presented in the paper.

On the basis of interviews with former students at the specific semester, we found indications that there was a low degree of integration between courses and projects [7]. Furthermore, a survey made by the general PBL Future research project covering the entire Aalborg University, showed that teachers across all faculties rated the importance of creating a connection between projects and courses, as one of the most important issues when practicing PBL [8].

The focus in this paper is based on the research question: *How can a change process of further integration between courses and semester project work be facilitated, and what are the benefits and concerns of using a planned organizational change management approach when changing a semester structure?*

For answering this question, we will present the case study and experimental research carried out at the 4th semester of the BSc engineering programme of Medialogy. Relevant data will be used for analyzing the process of change towards a higher integration of courses and projects, and the different methodological approaches framing the initiative will be discussed.

3 METHOD

3.1 The specific semester case

The engineering education at 4th semester of Medialogy in Copenhagen has normally been driven by 4 course teachers plus teaching assistants. Supervision of students' projects will involve a number of other teachers, depending of the number of project groups formed at semester start. In the specific semester examined by this paper, the course teachers were connected to both courses and supervision. The general semester theme framing the academic direction was 'Sound Computing and Sensor Technology'. The three courses consolidating the theme were Audio Processing (AP), Physical Interface Design (PID), and Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE). The courses' content rely more on math and programming than previous semesters. Many students fail at the ordinary course exams, and passed students generally consider it a difficult semester. On a grade scale where 2 is the grade needed for passing the course and 12 is the highest grade, the average course grading in 2018 were: AP: 3,5. PID: 1,7. DAE: 4,8. The low scores were a motivating factor for teachers to develop the semester and partake in the experimental research project.

3.2 Data sources

In this case study [9] we have been working with experimental methods inspired by co-creation [10] and ethnographic approaches [11] including experimental ethnography [12]. This means that we have been working with a research design as

something that develops in line with the study itself. The empirical basis for this paper consists of three different kinds of data, concerning the development and collaboration process with the 5 teachers of 4th semester at Medialogy.

3.3 Data

30 August 2018 and 23 November 2018	Minutes from meetings with teachers	Agenda for meeting: Introduction to PBL Future and status
April 2019	Semi-structured individual interviews with teachers A-E	Interview focus: Teachers' experiences, the initiatives done at the flipped and integrated semester, communication, and problems on the way
June 2018	Pilot interview with 11 students from Audio Processing Media Technology 2018	Interview focus: Evaluation of the course
December 2018	Survey with previous 4 th semester students 2018	Survey focus: Evaluation of 4 th semester

Minutes from the meetings have been used for documenting how development and decisions have materialized along the way, leading towards the change process.

The semi-structured, video-recorded interviews, performed with each of the teachers, have been the primary data for reflection on the planning process. All 5 interviews were filmed and fully transcribed. A thematic analysis has been made for coding the data in the following categories; motivation for change, communication, integration, flipped learning and problems. In this paper, the categories of communication and integration will be used for shedding light on the research question [13]. The videos lasted 35 minutes on average, recorded in clips of 20-30 minutes (therefore they are labelled v1-v3). Furthermore, a small pilot interview with 11 students attending the AP course from the past year's (2018) semester was performed, to investigate issues in the teaching practice. Additionally, a survey was performed with all students attending the 2018 4th semester, to investigate possible problems across the 4th semester courses.

4 UNFREEZING

4.1 The need for change

In the first step of *changing* the 4th semester structure, the current ways of doing things had to be “unfrozen”. The teachers need to see that change is necessary. Well established customs and social habits can work as inner resistance to change, and this has to be broken [14]. In the case of 4th semester, the motivation to change was pretty clear. The AP course had a lot of failing students and in the interview, evaluations done by the research group, the teachers could see a lot of criticism towards the course. The PID course was also failing a lot of students and the main teacher at the course quickly agreed to participate in the change process. Meanwhile, the DAE course was a bit different. The DAE teacher had already changed the course to a flipped course 4 years prior. Since the flip, it had shown better results in student gradings. This DAE teacher played the role of first initiator and a good example, showing that the flipped learning approach can work. To support the motivation and show why a change was needed, the research group made the survey on previous 4th semester students of 2018, which indicated problems when looking at how courses and projects supported each other. The students reported that especially regarding the AP and PID courses, they had difficulties to transfer course content to their semester projects [7]. This feedback from students should work as motivation for change - not just to a flipped learning approach, but also to create a better integration between courses and semester project work. The teachers all announced that they were very motivated to participate in this process of change (Minutes, 30 Aug 2018). “Unfreezing” is not always necessary if the participants already is prepared to change and it seemed to be the case at 4th semester.

4.2 An action research strategy

Lewin’s POCM model is built on action research [15] and to develop the concept of a flipped and integrated 4th semester and thereby entering the “change step”, action research methods were used [16,17]. Action research implies continuous cooperation between researchers and participants and together they determine goals and action to implement the goals. Keeping all involved parties, both teachers and researchers, informed about interventions and results at all times is very important [15]. The research team therefore planned to meet with the teachers frequently in the fall of 2018, to develop the flipped and integrated semester that was to be implemented in spring 2019 [7]. This showed to be a substantial challenge. The teachers found the process to be too time demanding and would rather do the development meetings themselves (Mail from C, 13 Sep 2018). A teacher later explained that *“it made no sense to have meetings with 8 people, when we are only 5 people running the courses. We teachers needed to talk together in terms of the content”* (Interview, C, v1, 6.38). This feeling of being pressured on time and wishing to develop the new semester without the researchers being part of the development, resonated between teachers. It was a turning point for how to manage the change process, and the researcher team stepped back a bit, to find a more sensitive approach and another balance, using the planned organizational change management approach vs. a more emergent approach.

4.3 The change

Doing the change, Lewin describes as 'reeducation'. It is more than just to acquire new information, habits or skills, it is to change knowledge, values, standards and emotions

within the behavior patterns that are enacted in norms and interpersonal relations. Therefore Lewin puts great emphasis on the social aspect of making a change successful [18]. Research shows that 70% of adults' knowledge is fully automated and unconscious [19] and changing habits and behavioral patterns is extremely difficult. Lewin says:

“Only by anchoring his conduct in something as large, substantial and superindividual as the culture of the group, can the individual stabilize his new beliefs sufficiently to keep them immune from the day-by-day fluctuations of moods and influences to which he, as an individual, is subject” [18, p. 59]

The research group had planned to be part of the support group, supporting a new culture, keeping them on the track with the change. Meanwhile, as teachers gravitated towards each other instead, the research group adapted and stepped backwards, allowing the teacher group to form their own supporting group, for each other, for the change ahead. It also meant reformulating the POCM approach, where action research principles is the main tool for management; letting the change initiative come from a collaboration between teachers and researchers, to a more sensitive and emergent way where the teachers had more autonomy. A bricolage approach was chosen.

4.4 Change by a bricolage approach

Change and innovation done by a more ‘ad hoc’ approach, that is based on the needs of the participants, has been demonstrated before [20]. Claude Lévi-Strauss introduces the notion of bricolage to describe a particular mode, in which humans relate to their environment through practical reasoning. Bricolage is by Lévi-Strauss characterized as a particular way of acting as “doing things with whatever is at hand” [21], as opposed to doing things in prescribed systematic ways.

Innovation and institutional change is often only acknowledged when pushed from higher-level management, while the day-to-day innovations created by practitioners are not acknowledged to the same degree. But Fuglsang and Sørensen discuss a more practice-based perspective on development, innovation and deals, in a case study where innovation from employees can be recognized in the organisational processes [22]. They describe three levels of working with innovation and institutional change: 1) Top management-initiated innovation, 2) Management-mediated innovation, 3) Bricolage [22]. Going from the action research approach, where the researchers are in constant collaboration with the practitioners, to a bricolage approach, the development of a flipped and integrated semester concept was up to the teacher group themselves to a high degree. To support the teachers as much as possible in this process, the research group now found themselves more as management-mediators, instead of co-creators.

4.5 Management mediators supporting the teacher group

Letting the teacher group develop and change semester structure as bricoleurs, meant that the researchers had to step back and let the teacher group do the development. Management, at this time, was focused on negotiating for more resources from the top management. The teacher group sought IT tools to support the integration between the AP and PID courses, and resources for a research assistant that could support the teaching at both of these courses. This research assistant became an important

communication link in a culture where it showed that teachers weren't used to talking much together. In previous years, the communication across the semester's courses had not been that active:

“Definitely we [the teachers] are talking more together this semester. Several years ago, I was co-teaching this course and I don't remember talking to anyone about what is happening on the other courses [...]. We didn't talk, I didn't know what was happening. Now I have a much more clear idea of what is going on in the other courses.” (Interview, A, v2, 19.39).

The research assistant played an important role in this communication. He described the communication as still being a problem and that his role as connected to both courses became an important communication link:

“Between courses it was pretty tough, I still haven't managed to get [both teachers] in the same room for a meeting. They both get second-hand information from me, because I meet both doing classes. I don't think it was a problem though. I would say – most of the communication was done through me, [one teacher] would ask questions of what [the other teacher] was doing, or I would just tell them both what was happening in the other class - bringing them up to date” (Interview, B, v2, 6.35).

Having a research assistant that were directly connected to two of the three courses became a very important part of creating better integration. The communication culture between the teachers as a whole group, however, became a problem. At a meeting in November 2018 during the preparation phase, it was clear that teachers hadn't yet succeeded finding time to discuss and plan the flipped and integrated semester concept, towards the upcoming spring 2019 semester (Minutes, Nov. 2018). They believed they didn't have time, and hadn't been able to schedule meetings for development. And thereby, did not manage by themselves, to support each other in the change. The research group then interfered, and started scheduling meetings with teachers again, where the top priority was to facilitate a space, shared simultaneously by the teachers, for talking together and developing the semester structure. One of the teachers describe the researchers' role as followed:

“They [the research group] have the integration role. We as teachers know our own course and know how we can try out new things here, but we don't know the other courses. The PBL Future team brought us together and made us understand this integration effort.” (Interview, A, v2, 3.05).

Putting emphasis on integration hasn't come by itself for the teachers. Development of the separate courses seemed to be easier to do on their own, but innovating towards integration between courses seemed to be difficult for the teachers. Still on the sideline, in the balance of planning the change and mediating the innovation, the research group in higher degree now tried to become an implicit part of the teacher group, supporting the communication and the common goal of change. The research team were around when the teachers had lectures, they kept asking questions, they observed, and did surveys focusing on the integration. Information about what the teachers did and how it worked were given as instant feedback and the research group thereby supported the teacher group by giving them information about the practice of the 4th semester. This was balancing towards a more action research approach -

gathering data about practice that can be part of co-creating change process, the teachers accepted and appreciated. One teacher says:

“When the semester actually started running I think it has been very helpful to get your interview feedback from the students, because that is something we usually don’t get. They don’t answer the online surveys and it is very useful to read the comments from the students. And also to have you there to sample the lectures and know that afterwards we can look back at this material and maybe evaluate it in a coherent way – that is nice.” (Interview, C, v1, 6.38)

The research team have thereby not just been mediators for innovation, but had to obtain a balance with the role of change management, along the way.

5 THE BALANCE OF MANAGEMENT AND BRICOLAGE

Letting the practitioners of the change be bricoleurs and doing the change by what they are motivated by, can be beneficial in a busy scheduled working situation. However balancing between the POCM approach and the bricolage approach in the middle of it all can create concerns, because the bricolage approach might need more defined end goals. One of the teachers expressed that she would have liked more guidance:

“When you are a group that don’t really know what a typical semester project would look like on the semester, it has been difficult to talk constructively about the change. So ideally you would start from the project and then think, what would be a good ideal semester project and how can we support that and the learning goals within the different courses. Maybe that should have been the starting point – to make it more tangible for us” (Interview, C, v1, 8.11).

The teacher quote explains the integration strategy that the teachers developed in collaboration. It isn't necessarily the only way to build the integration concept, as other integration strategies using more structurally based integration or problem-oriented integration, might as well have been implemented [23]. But letting the teachers define the concept themselves in an action research-theoretical framework, may have amplified engagement and motivation [16]. Looking at the teacher quote above and knowing that the teachers in high degree did the change as bricoleurs they might have needed more guidance. The balance between planned change and a more emergent bricolage approach is difficult. Fuglsang and Sørensen is pointing out a problem of 'disconnection', that can occur between the management initiators, management mediators and the bricoleurs. A disconnection that in the case of 4th semester Medialogy might be seen in the huge communication challenges between the teachers. If the communication culture of a teacher group, that are to create integration between their courses, isn't that well-functioning, there is a risk of losing the support in a group. Thereby, the change management has to be balanced in a delicate, attentive manner.

5.1 Reflections on benefits and concerns when facilitating change of a semester structure

The bigger, structural changes performed in this case study at the 4th semester at Medialogy in AAU, CPH, has shown some problems in how to approach the change

management process. How much has a change to be facilitated, and how much are practitioners themselves able to initiate and define their change. Using Lewin's planned organizational change management model rooted in action research, it is important that the practitioners themselves are involved in the design of the change. This is an engaging and motivational factor for the practitioners. What we have met in this experimental case study, is that the action research approach didn't fit with the silo-thinking of the teaching practice at the 4th semester Medialogy. The teachers were engaged in changing to a flipped and integrated semester, but they didn't want to engage and spend the time with the research group in co-creating what and how the change was to be done. Initiating a change process where integration between the courses were a goal it made a lot of sense that the teacher group themselves grouped up and worked on figuring out what and how the flipped and integrated semester should look like. Using a bricolage approach thereby became an important tool for developing and changing the 4th semester structure, because it gave the teachers autonomy to work on the change themselves. However we found a communication culture between the teachers that made it hard for the teacher group to find and articulate a common change process, and to be effective in the development of the change. The research team needed to balance some structured meetings and create communication links across the semester. Both the planned organizational change management approach and the bricolage approach showed benefits and concerns. The bricolage approach let the teachers themselves work with changing the semester structure, and a lot of change was seen, especially implementing the flipped learning approach. However, it still didn't bring teachers out of their silo-thinking, but in this case, the role of innovating mediators was important for other reasons, for instance, as the negotiating of the extra resource of an across working research assistant that linked the communication across two of the courses. Also, planned organizational change management was important, to support the communication between teachers. Planned meetings were necessary to ensure the alignment of teachers' schedule, for discussion and development of the flipped and integrated semester. The mix of a structured and planned change approach, and a bricolage approach, has in many ways worked well for developing a more integrated semester structure. This may be of inspiration to other development initiatives, at engineering education programmes. The approach has helped removing communication barriers, as an ongoing, dynamic balance between open-ended and more structured change development processes.

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